

Wilkinson, Laura J. & Skinner, Katherine (2023) Focus groups 3: slides, Focus groups 2023-Q1, Book Analytics Dashboard (BAD) Demonstration Project (2022-2025), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7780564>

WELCOME!

Book Analytics Dashboard (BAD) Focus Group

[date of session]

EDUCOPIA
INSTITUTE

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Open Access

 Curtin University

 Mellon
Foundation

Do you consent to recording?

Audio of this focus group will be recorded and possibly transcribed. We will use the recording and possible transcription solely to support our project efforts. If the project team ever considers any other uses, we would reach out to you beforehand to obtain your informed consent.

With that understanding, do you consent to today's focus group being recorded? Do you have any questions about the process? Please signal your willingness to participate in this recorded focus group by stating "yes" in the chat window.

Please share with us your name, organization, and your favorite childhood book

Background and Context

The Book Analytics Dashboard project is building on an earlier Mellon-funded initiative: **Developing a Pilot Data Trust for OA eBook Usage (2020 – 2022)**.

Moving from a Pilot to a Service

The 2022 - 2025 **Book Analytics Dashboard project will:**

- **Scale** dashboard infrastructure and workflows
- Develop a dashboard **service**, including customer support
- Explore & implement a long-term plan for housing, maintenance and funding

Key features: not-for-profit hosting, governed by stakeholders, lock-in avoidant

Source of truth for BAD metadata: ONIX feed

Current usage data sources

- JSTOR
- GoogleBooks
- OAPEN via IRUS UK
- Crossref Event Data
- Google Analytics - used by ANU Press (this is quite bespoke)
- UCL Discovery - used by UCL Press

Currently being explored

- IRUS
 - Fulcrum as a case study
- Project MUSE

Possible in future years

- Open Alex
- EBSCO
- SciELO books
- Clarivate
- Amazon
- Internet Archive
- Science Open

Latest Prototype (Data Looker, aka Data Studio)

OVERVIEW

Drilldown for more details

AUTHORS

GLOBAL REACH

SUBJECTS

EVENTS & IMPACT

ABOUT

Global Reach - Countries, Institutions & Cities

Book access by Country, Institution, and City

Countries/Territories Reached **227** Total Access (exc. Mentions) **1,547,034**

Select Country

Book Downloads **297,523**

Chapter Downloads **1,249,511**

Access by Countries

Chapter downloads from JSTOR **1,249,511**

Book downloads from OAPEN **296,453**

Book downloads from Google Books **1,070**

Country / Territory	Total Access
United States	2,247,625
United Kingdom	511,458
India	319,849
Philippines	249,690
Canada	248,148
Germany	215,680
China	183,265
Australia	161,945
Netherlands	101,346
Indonesia	89,315

Access by Institutions

Institution	Access from JSTOR
University of Toronto, Toronto	3,322
INFLIBNET as administrator of eShodhSindhu Consortium - ESS Office	3,306
New York University	3,179
King's College, London	3,000
Columbia University	2,876
University of Exeter	2,790
Macquarie University	2,589
University of Edinburgh	2,578
University of Bristol	2,525

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Access by Cities

Developed by the 'Book Analytics Dashboard Project (2022-2025)' technical team.

**Have you used dashboards for
business intelligence in the past?**

Which ones and how?

**What could you accomplish with
these dashboards that would
further your own efforts?**

**Which features are essential and
which are desirable? Why?**

**What features are we currently
missing that you feel are
important?**

Who from your team will be the primary user(s) of the dashboards?

**If we build a standard/premium or
standard/à la carte model, what
belongs in each?**

**What pricing range would you
expect for the service?
How much lead time do you need?**

Who from your team will be involved in the signing of legal agreements?

**What community governance
qualities or characteristics
would you want and expect
for this service?**

Book Analytics Dashboards (2022-2025)

Project Background

The Book Analytics Dashboard Project (2022-2025) is focused on creating a sustainable OA Book focused analytics service. This service is needed to safeguard and support diversity in the voices, perspectives, geographies, topics and languages made visible through OA Books. Funded by the [Mellon Foundation](#), the Book Analytics Dashboard project is building on an earlier Mellon-funded initiative: [Developing a Pilot Data Trust for OA eBook Usage \(2020 – 2022\)](#). In addition to scaling workflows, infrastructure and customer support, the Demonstration Project is developing a long-term plan for housing, maintenance and funding of the analytics service as a sustainable community infrastructure.

Formal Project Title: OA Book Usage Analytics for Diverse Communities – A Demonstration Project

Short Title: Book Analytics Dashboard Project

Duration: April 2022 – April 2025

Funders: [Mellon Foundation](#), [COARD](#)

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